

Implementation of Perkasal Policy Number 38 of 2021 Regarding the Acceptance of Cadets and Cadets of the AL Navy Academy in a Gender Perspective

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ABSTRACT

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This research will examine the implementation of Policy Perkasal Number 38 of 2021 regarding the Admission of Cadets at the Indonesian Navy Academy (Akademi TNI AL) from a gender perspective. It will also explore the challenges faced in the implementation and efforts to overcome these challenges within the framework of Policy Perkasal Number 38 of 2021. The research will focus on the selection process of male and female cadets according to the mentioned policy.

The research methodology employed in this study is descriptive qualitative research. Data collection methods include interviews, observations, and literature reviews. The theoretical framework used in this research is the policy implementation theory according to Mazmanian and Paul A. Sabatier.

The findings of the research indicate that the implementation of this policy has not yet achieved gender equality and justice. Technical constraints and societal views that do not support equality remain significant challenges. The policy lacks clear objectives to prevent gender discrimination. Socio-economic conditions in Indonesia also influence the acceptance of male and female cadets. Factors affecting policy implementation involve ambiguity in gender-based quotas, lack of socialization, limited involvement of female soldiers in structural positions, high aspirations to enter non-military higher education institutions, decreasing interest in becoming civil servants, minimal facilities, heavy curriculum burdens, and a shortage of human resources.

Recommendations include establishing clear gender-based admission quotas, intensifying socialization efforts related to Policy Perkasal Number 38 of 2021, increasing the involvement of female soldiers in structural positions, adjusting the military education concept to the social context of women, and improving training facilities for prospective Indonesian Navy soldiers.

KEYWORDS:

Policy, Equality, Justice, Gender

INTRODUCTION

As an agency that plays an important role in upholding state sovereignty, the development of Indonesian National Army recruitment from a gender perspective is an urgency that needs to be implemented. The development of the Indonesian National Army's revenue from a gender perspective is becoming increasingly urgent to implement, because the world as a whole continues to experience

significant developments. The significant developments that occur are the implications of the ongoing industrial revolution 4.0 and digitalisation as a whole. The dynamics of rapid change, of course, have implications for rapid geopolitical change. Geopolitics itself can be understood as a mechanism used by a country in order to control and compete in its political territory (Flint, 2006: 13).

This shows that geopolitics is the relationship of a country to the political conditions that exist in its territory. The development of the capabilities of the Indonesian National Army in a gender perspective is absolutely necessary to be implemented because the state is essentially seen as an authority that has certain powers and authorities that are authorised to exercise rights and obligations as one part of the legal subject (Sulaiman, 2019: 143). This geopolitical pressure must certainly be addressed wisely and

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wisely. This means that the development of the views of the Indonesian National Army in a gender perspective must be carried out by looking at the circumstances in the field.

The development of the view of the Indonesian National Army from a gender perspective is a policy that is in line with the essence of the Indonesian National Army itself.

As a state agency engaged in the enforcement of state sovereignty. The Indonesian National Army can be classified as a form of legal profession. Sikum Pribadi asserts that a profession is a pledge (statement of promise) made by someone who wants to devote himself to a position for reasons of conscience (Supeno, 1995: 19). So it can be understood that the Indonesian National Army, which is one part of the legal profession, must be developed in line with the needs of the community and in accordance with the institution's services in the context of maintaining national sovereignty. The necessity to make a change of view in a gender perspective is also in line with the nature of the profession which is a field of work with a high index of need in social society (Sahertim, 1997: 27).

The public needs excellent and main service from a profession. In terms of human resource development (HR), the ratio of the number of personnel of the Indonesian National Army is one of the factors that must be considered. Specifically, an important concern is the ratio between male and female personnel. This comparison is important, because the Indonesian National Army as a state institution must be able to accommodate all elements that exist in the social community. More than that, the comparison of the number of male and female personnel is also closely related to the method of looking at the gender perspective related to what will be done.

The comparison between male and female personnel in policy review from a gender perspective in the Indonesian National Army is essentially a method of analysis based on psychological review. In the aspect of decision-making, men tend to base their understanding on logical buildings and will always be ready to face conflict (Trinovryan, 2016: 205). In a more complex understanding, women have two verbal centres in their brain and men only have a verbal centre in the left brain (Watra, 2018: 15). This condition is an indicator that confirms that women tend to have negotiator skills and men tend to choose to take steps to face conflict.

Based on this understanding and viewed from the perspective of the main tasks and functions of the Indonesian National Army, it can be understood that the comparison of the number of personnel based on gender is important to explain. The development of human resources (HR) of the Indonesian National Army will take place progressively, if the ratio between male and female personnel is close to equal numbers. Because in fact, the basic abilities of men and women are needed in the same and equal levels. There are 9 (nine) priority programmes in building the strength and

fostering the competence of the Navy, one of which is an effort to build the Navy's Human Resources (HR). In order to provide professional, modern and resilient HR results, the leadership of the Navy fosters systematically, directed and sustainable which includes Human Resources Development and Personnel Development of Navy soldiers (Yusuf, 2014).

Gender inequality is a long-standing problem where there is negative discrimination and different treatment for men and women by viewing men as masculine and women as feminine, which assumes that women are weak and unable to compete with men. The failure to reconstruct the building of equality between men and women in the context of the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL), in general, has started with the virginity test for prospective Taruni (Sally Joanna, Ida Bagus Wyasa Putra, and A. A. Sri Utara, 2018). Such conditions occur, due to the absorption of gender roles that are very concrete in the formation of role character. However, this policy certainly needs to be understood in depth, because patriarchal culture is still very deeply embedded in the institutional governance of the Indonesian National Navy (TNI AL) (Eschholz and J. Bufkin: 2011).

Table 1. Comparison of the Number of Naval Academy (AAL) Chassis

No	Tahun	Casis Taruna	Casis Taruni
1	2022	278	27
2	2021	223	22
3	2020*	87	10
4	2019	108	15

*) The number listed in 2020, is the number of those inducted as Juvenile Officers who graduated from the 65th Naval Academy (AAL).

Such conditions, of course, cannot be separated from the historical reality that negates the further involvement of men in war and women are protected legal subjects in war (D. P. Fry A. H. Gabriel, 1994). As an organisation that has superior performance, the Navy must also prioritise gender. The development of human resources (HR) of the Indonesian National Army will take place progressively, if the ratio between male and female personnel is close to an equal number. In the view of work life balance, equality is understood as equality at work and to avoid conflict (Novelia, 2013). Because in fact, the basic abilities of men and women are needed in equal and equal levels. Although needed at the same and equal levels, in fact the Indonesian National Army women only account for 15% of the ideal 30%. This conception is certainly better than Joshua S. Goldstein's view, which negates that the military is filled with 97 to 99 per cent men (Putriwiola Elian Nasir, 2014).

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Table 1.2. Number of cadets graduating from the Indonesian Navy Fiscal Year 2022

Academy	Number of Cadets - Cadets
Military Academy	292 Perwira
police Academy	246 Perwira
Air Force Academy	109 Perwira
Naval Academy	107 Perwira

Source: Indonesian Navy Observation Data

When practising gender mainstreaming in the Navy, it will certainly have a huge impact on both the Navy and the surrounding environment. The duties of members of the Navy have a very high social impact in the community because they are in direct contact with the community as well. Gender mainstreaming that is practiced by members of the Navy in the field, will be an example for the community that the Navy is an organisation that continues to support government policies. So that gender mainstreaming in the Navy will also play a role as a driver of gender equality and gender justice in society. Gender mainstreaming in etymological studies is understood as a strategy carried out by development to integrate gender into 1 (one) integral dimension of efforts to plan, compile, implement, monitor and evaluate development policies, programmes and activities in the region. As explained in Article 1 paragraph (1) of the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 15 of 2008 concerning General Guidelines for the Implementation of Gender Mainstreaming in the Region.

With the role of the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL) as a driver of gender equality and justice in society, the argument about the conflict between gender equality and eastern culture is something that can be broken. Because until now there are still many historical arguments that are negatively narrated about gender equality. One of these negative narratives, in this case, is that gender equality is a Western philosophy of life that is too individualistic (Zainal Abidin, 2015).

Furthermore, it is explained in the Presidential Instruction of the Republic of Indonesia Number 9 of 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in National Development, that in order to improve the position, role and quality of women, as well as efforts to realise gender equality and justice in family life, society, nation and state, it is deemed necessary to carry out a gender mainstreaming strategy into the entire national development process. Moreover, gender mainstreaming into the entire development process is an integral part of the functional activities of all government agencies and institutions at the Central and Regional levels. Therefore, in connection with the above matters and in order to encourage, streamline, and optimise gender mainstreaming efforts in an integrated and coordinated manner, it is deemed necessary to issue a Presidential Instruction.

From the background description above, it can be concluded that gender mainstreaming in the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) is very important because in addition to supporting government policies, it is also related to TNI AL tasks such as the activities of TNI AL members who play a role in handling domestic violence and also the involvement of policewomen to participate in TNI AL strategic policy making. An understanding of the implementation of gender mainstreaming policies and the factors that influence them is needed so that it can be used to change the perception of masculine Navy members to be gender-friendly in the workplace.

History records the development of gender equality that occurred within the framework of the Indonesian National Army, starting in 1960 when the Army Commander issued Army Commander Decree Number 1056/12/1960 concerning the Establishment of the Army Women's Corps (KOWAD) which was then followed by the same decision by the Commander of the Navy and Commander of the Air Force (Handayani, 2008: 11-12). The essential purpose of the concept of gender equality in the Navy's framework is to provide rights, obligations, and honour to Indonesian women and serve the country through the military (Zulvyani, 2019: 136). Such a policy is certainly in line with the mandate described in Law Number 39 of 1999 concerning Human Rights (HAM). This law explains that the Indonesian rule of law applies the law fairly and without discrimination. What is meant by discrimination is any form of restriction, harassment, or exclusion that occurs either directly or indirectly, based on human differences such as religion, tribe, race, ethnicity, group, social class, economic status, gender, language, and political beliefs. This discrimination can result in the reduction, deviation, or even elimination of the recognition, exercise, or enjoyment of human rights and fundamental freedoms, both in individual and collective life, in areas such as p

This assertion is explained in Article 1 paragraph (3) of Law No. 39/1999 on Human Rights and in Article 3 paragraphs (1), (2), and (3) of Law No. 39/1999 on Human Rights, the following aspects are explained:

1. Every person is born free with equal human dignity and is endowed with a pure mind and heart to live in society, nation, and state in a spirit of brotherhood.
2. Every person is entitled to recognition, guarantees, protection and fair legal treatment as well as legal certainty and equal treatment before the law.
3. Everyone has the right to the protection of human rights and basic human freedoms, without discrimination.

In a more complex discussion, this is related to the Indonesian National Army (TNI) aspect. In the Department of Peacekeeping Operations (DPKO) study, this is a concern in the "Policy on Gender Equality in Peacekeeping Operations". The discussion on gender equality, in this case, of course, is specifically related to the number of cadets and

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Taruni candidates for the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL). Where in this case there is a concrete gap, between the number of cadets and cadets accepted.

Such problems are the basis for this research. This research will specifically discuss the implementation of the Navy cadet and cadet recruitment policy from a gender perspective. This research is an effort of renewal, in order to create a progressive Indonesian National Army. Progressive reform means enforcing the law with determination, empathy, dedication, the same commitment and courage that is in line with the policy of finding other ways than what is usually done (Farkhani, 2018: 177). Specifically, this research will analyse issues regarding the implementation of the Chief of Naval Staff Regulation (PERKASAL) Number 38 of 2021 concerning Gender in the Perspective of the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL).

What will be the basis for this research is the Mazmanian and Sabatier model of public policy. This model of public policy implementation was chosen on the grounds that this model will produce comprehensive research and make the research more towards reality. The comprehensiveness produced in this research comes from the Mazmanian and Sabatier model, which has relevance to the problems to be studied. Although sociologically it has succeeded in implementing gender equality, the social reality that occurs within the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL) shows the opposite fact. Determination of female soldiers in the assignment of tasks and authority is the first thing that negates this condition. In addition to negating such conditions, determination also occurs in terms of rank. It is rare for female soldiers to have a high level of rank, as is generally the case with soldiers of the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL). Such problems, which then present a consequence of the importance of gender equality in the perspective of the Indonesian military.

In further understanding, this research is a method of analysis that has relevance to the realisation of gender equality within the Indonesian Navy. It needs to be understood that gender equality within the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) is not only related to developments that occur in Indonesian society. The analysis of gender equality in the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL), in this study, is explained in relation to the implementation of the Navy cadet and cadet admission policy in a gender perspective in the Regulation of the Chief of Naval Staff (Perkasal) Number 38 of 2021 concerning Admission of Cadets and Cadets of the Indonesian National Army Academy (TNI AL).

RESEARCH METHOD

The research method used in this research is descriptive qualitative research. Descriptive qualitative research is a research method that utilises qualitative data and is described descriptively. Descriptive qualitative research is often used to analyse events, phenomena, or social conditions.

Qualitative research is a particular tradition in social science that fundamentally joins the observation of humans in their own areas and relates to these people in their language and in their terms (Mudjiyanto, 2018: 88).

As a normative research, this research uses qualitative method as its analysis method. Qualitative method is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or oral words from data sources that are observed and researched (Moleong 2000: 3). In qualitative methods, the researcher is the key instrument of the research itself. The data analysis technique used in this study refers to the concept of Miles, Huberman and Saidana (2014), namely :

a. Data collection

Data collection in qualitative research, the data collection process is carried out before research, during research, and even at the end of research. Data collection can be carried out using the mechanism of interviews, observation, and in this case also includes literature study. Interview is a mechanism carried out in order to seek information, using an informative-based approach. This means that this research was carried out, by conducting interactive question and answer activities. Interactive questions and answers carried out in this case, of course, must be adjusted to the needs of the research itself.

b. Data condensation

Data condensation refers to the process of shrinking or combining relevant information to present a topic or findings in a concise manner. In research with the title "Implementation of Perkasal Policy Number 38 of 2021 concerning Acceptance of Cadets and Cadets of the Indonesian Navy Academy in a Gender Perspective," data condensation can be done by summarising the main findings related to the implementation of the policy. This technique involves analysing gender aspects in the acceptance of cadets and cadets, including their impact on gender equality and justice within the TNI AL Academy. Conclusions can include an evaluation of the effectiveness of the policy, challenges faced, and recommendations for improving the implementation of the policy in the context of a gender perspective.

c. Presentation of data

Data presentation is done after the reduction process. Presentation of data is the process of providing a set of information that has been compiled which makes it possible to draw conclusions. The process of presenting this data is to reveal the whole of the group of data obtained so that it is easy to read, so that researchers can understand what is happening in the research scene and what researchers do in anticipating it.

d. Conclusion

The conclusion in the series of qualitative data analysis according to the interactive model proposed by Miles, Huberman and Saidana (2014) essentially contains a description of all sub-categorised themes listed in the

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completed categorisation and coding table accompanied by verbatim interview quotes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Implementation of Perkasal Policy Number 38 of 2021 concerning Acceptance of Cadets and Taruni of the TNI Academy

The policy implementation model proposed by Mazmanian and Sabatier (1983), refers to 3 (three) variables that influence the success of policy implementation, namely problem characteristics, policy characteristics and policy scope. The complexity of the problems faced in realising the Chief of Naval Staff Regulation Number 38 of 2021, which is used to develop human resources within the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) based on a gender perspective, presents a consequence of the importance of institutional development through a systemic and integrative approach. Such an analysis is of course closely correlated with the essence of the problems or obstacles that occur. In addition, this analysis is also based on efforts to resolve the obstacles faced effectively and efficiently. Where the effective and efficient resolution of obstacles in this case, requires the integration of actions and synchronisation of policy programs. So that none of the policies can be taken separately, because it will have the potential to produce competent value.

Thus, policies that can be taken to produce an integrative solution to optimise the implementation of the Chief of Naval Staff Regulation (Perkasal) Number 38 of 2021, which is used to develop human resources within the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) based on a gender perspective, include the following:

a. *Providing Clear Restrictions on the Quota for Gender-Based Acceptance of Candidates for Soldiers of the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL)*

The first aspect that needs to be optimised to form the maturity of the concept of the Chief of Naval Staff Regulation (Perkasal) Number 38 of 2021, in this research study is about how the mechanism of the process of accepting prospective Indonesian Navy Soldiers (TNI AL) is a clear gender-based quota restriction. This mechanism must then be realised into an important value in the form of the development of the Indonesian National Navy (TNI AL), as an important state institution capable of realising gender equality. Gender equality in this case, is an aspect of how the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) must provide opportunities for women to become active soldiers. In addition to providing opportunities for women to become active servicemen, the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) in this case must provide a wide space for women to have a career.

The implementation of the quota restriction for female Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) candidates, in this case, is an effort to protect all interests without any negative values. With a firm effort, the protection of gender equality can be realised to the fullest. This means that this concept must be

implemented first and foremost. This problem then becomes a firm value, about how prospective female Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) Soldiers have equal opportunities.

b. *Disseminating the Regulation of the Chief of Naval Staff (Perkasal) Number 38 of 2021*

The implementation of the socialisation of the Chief of Naval Staff Regulation (Perkasal) Number 38 of 2021, of course, is the second value that must be carried out optimally. This implementation is a form of explanation and affirmation to the public, that the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) provides ample space for men and women to participate as candidates for active Soldiers of the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL). This value must certainly be the concept of affirmation, about how the law is returned to the community. Socialisation in this case can be a form of giving opportunities to the community, to decide what attitude they will take on the enactment of normativeism. In addition to carrying out socialisation to provide explanations, socialisation in this case is a form of openness and a means of testing normative rules in real actions in the social community.

c. *Increasing the Involvement of Active Women Soldiers in Structural Positions of the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL)*

Another aspect that must be implemented in this case, of course, is to increase the active involvement of Women Soldiers of the Indonesian National Navy (TNI AL). Active involvement in this case, must be carried out in the form of assigning structural positions to them. So that the Women Soldiers of the Indonesian National Navy (TNI AL), are not only given space for administrative positions. In a simple discussion, the concept in question is the expansion of work space and authority. So that the Women Soldiers of the Indonesian National Navy (TNI AL) are not only given to domestic work spaces, but also to work spaces that are central and play a major role in institutional development.

d. *Adjusting the Concept of Military Education for the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) with Women's Sociology*

The development of paradigms that exist in the daily life or sociology of women, of course, must be responded wisely by the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL). In this case, the aspect that is understood as a response is a form of change or adjustment between habits and the reality that occurs. This adjustment is a form of affirmation that the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL) is not a rigid and unchangeable state institution. Changes must still occur in the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL), to ensure the availability of Women Soldiers of the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL). This means that the Indonesian National Army Navy (TNI AL) should not become synonymous with a patriarchal national military unit. The concept of adjusting the education pattern of the Indonesian Navy for women is also a concrete affirmation that this institution is able to accommodate all aspects of the country's needs.

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e. *Providing Training Facilities and Infrastructure for Prospective Soldiers of the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL)*

This aspect can be implemented by building concrete facilities and infrastructure in each unit of the Indonesian Navy (TNI AL). This conception is an attempt to ensure that state institutions are not only looking for quality human resources (HR) but are also directly involved in shaping human resources (HR). This policy will be a fundamental understanding, which will be able to build a progressive paradigm. The state must be present to participate in the aspects of creating and improving the quality of human resources (HR) for female candidates for the Indonesian National Navy (TNI AL). The provision of training and health checking facilities in line with the Indonesian National Navy (TNI AL), must be carried out as a form of investment as well as an affirmation that the state not only takes but also creates.

4.3. Implementation of Perkasal Policy Number 38 of 2021 concerning Acceptance of Cadets and Cadets of the TNI Academy in a Gender Perspective

a. *Gender Equality*

Gender equality means equal conditions between men and women in terms of getting the same opportunities and rights as humans. Gender equality will be realised if in society there is no discrimination arising from differences between men and women. Sex differences often lead to gender differences that lead to injustice. In the model proposed by Mazmanian in the implementation of Perkasal Number 38 of 2021, there are several variables which will then become a review to analyse the Perkasal Number 38 of 2021 policy. Some of these variables will be described in the following explanation:

1. Variables whether the problem is easy to control or not

In this variable there are several things that support it. The first variable is regarding technical difficulties which ultimately results in the conclusion that the problem of gender discrimination in the admission of cadets and cadets to the Indonesian Navy is a problem that is difficult to solve because there are still many views regarding the lack of understanding of gender equality. Second, regarding the uniformity of behavior of the target group as meant by cadets and cadets, it results in the conclusion that there are various challenges that arise due to the heterogeneity of the cadets and cadets themselves. Third, regarding the percentage of the target group in proportion to the population, it explains that the ratio between cadets and the number of cadets and cadets in the acceptance of the Indonesian Navy is very small compared to the acceptance of cadets so that the target group constitutes a small portion of the population. Fourth, regarding the scope of desired behavioral changes. With the existence of this policy, gender discrimination is slowly starting to change with an increase in the number of cadets, but it is still experiencing several obstacles. This will lead to the conclusion that the existence of this policy will determine

that it is changing attitudes or behavior so that it tends to be quite difficult to implement.

2. Variable Policy Ability to Structure the Implementation Process

There are several that explain these variables. First, regarding clarity of objectives, it concludes that policies do not yet have clear and consistent objectives when viewed from a gender perspective. Second, regarding the use of adequate causal theory, this policy has been supported by clear regulations even though it is not yet consistent in prohibiting gender discrimination. Third, the appropriate allocation of funding sources means that capital in implementing this policy has been budgeted well and in implementing this policy funding has been provided from the government. Fourth, the hierarchical integration of the implementation of this policy needs to be emphasized with sanctions for individual agencies who do not implement it. Fifth, the decision rules of the implementing agency, which in this case is the Indonesian Navy recruitment team, result in the implementation of this policy being hampered by inconsistent orders from agencies related to gender equality. Sixth, the recruitment of implementing officials means that the commitment of the apparatus in implementing policies is strong enough to carry out their duties. Seventh, matters regarding formal access to external parties result in the need for increased support from external parties, namely the community.

3. Variables outside the policy that influence the implementation process

There are several things that explain variables outside the policy that influence the implementation process. First, sub-indicators of socio-economic and technological conditions which result in the socio-economic conditions of society being an obstacle in implementing this policy, but technological conditions actually make it easier to implement the policy. Second, sub-public support will result in the need for large public support to support the implementation of this policy. Third, the attitudes and resources of the groups result in the conclusion that there is a need for a forum for criticizing voter groups. Fourth, the commitment and leadership ability of implementing officials concludes that it is necessary to realize the objectives of this policy clearly

b. *Gender Justice*

Gender pays more attention to aspects of a person's masculinity or femininity. Where gender plays a role in seeing the identity and various characteristics that are different between men and women. However, these differences often give rise to injustice. This injustice is caused by the non-fulfillment of basic human rights for women and men.

Justice comes from the basic word fair, which means siding with what is right and adhering to the truth or just

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characteristics, actions and treatment. In the Big Indonesian Dictionary, the word fair means fair, impartial and impartial. Gender justice is a process and fair treatment of women and men. Gender justice means there is no standardization of roles, double burdens, subordination, marginalization and violence against women and men. Meanwhile, gender equality is equal conditions for men and women to obtain opportunities and rights as human beings.

Gender justice is the creation of equal conditions and status for men and women in order to obtain opportunities and enjoy their rights as human beings so that they both have the same role. Gender justice leads women and men towards equality where conditions and status are equal to obtain opportunities and enjoy their rights as human beings so that they are able to play a role and participate in development, politics, economics, social, culture, education, defense and security in enjoying the results of this development. Gender injustice that is socialized to men and women will steadily result in this injustice becoming a habit and ultimately it is believed that gender roles are natural and ultimately accepted by society in general. This is because there are errors or confusion in the meaning of gender because basically gender, which is a social construction, is considered to be natural, which means God's provision.

Factors that perpetuate gender inequality include:

- 1) Patriarchal culture
- 2) Economic system
- 3) Belief system or religious interpretation
- 4) Social customs
- 5) Political system
- 6) Education system

Gender inequality is a system and structure where men and women are victims of that system. In order to understand how gender differences have resulted in gender injustice, it can be understood through various manifestations of this injustice, including:

- 1) The process of marginalization and impoverishment of women
- 2) Subordination of women's work
- 3) Stereotyping of women's work
- 4) Violence against women
- 5) Heavier workload

Efforts that must be made to achieve gender equality appear to be not just individual, but must be joint and institutional, especially from parties who have authority and play a role in the gender formation process. For this reason, the role of policy makers and development planning is very important and determines the direction of change towards gender equality or it could be said that the state or government has a role/contribution in realizing gender balance. The realization of gender equality and gender justice is characterized by the absence of discrimination between women and men, so that they have (APKM) access, opportunities to participate and control over development and

obtain equal and fair benefits. Having access and participation means having the opportunity or chance to use resources and having the authority to make decisions regarding how to use and the results of these resources. Having control means having full authority to make decisions over the use and results of resources. So that you get the same benefits from development. Government policies regarding gender must be socialized in development aspects, for example education, culture, economics, politics and others.

In Perkasal policy Number 38 of 2021, it was found that there were still substances that did not support gender justice from the substance that still did not provide gender equality. In accepting cadets and cadets, if gender equality has not been found, gender justice can emerge. So it is necessary to update the substance of gender justice in the policy to be more targeted and provide appropriate sanctions for its formation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis explained in the previous discussion, it can be concluded that:

1. Implementation of Perkasal policy Number 38 of 2021 concerning Admission of Cadets and Cadets to the Indonesian Navy Academy towards a gender equality perspective on indicators and sub-indicators:
 - a. The scope of desired behavioral changes shows indications of an increase in the number of cadets so that gender equality begins to emerge.
 - b. Existing causal theories also support gender equality.
 - c. The allocation of financial resources is adequate to provide gender equality in the recruitment of cadets and cadets.
 - d. The existing hierarchy is in accordance with implementation needs.
 - e. The decision rules of the implementing agency are consistent with the aims and objectives of this policy.
 - f. The recruitment process for implementing officials is also adequate to achieve gender equality.
 - g. There is public support in realizing gender equality in the implications of this policy.
 - h. There is commitment and competence from implementing officials to provide gender equality.
2. Implementation of Perkasal policy Number 38 of 2021 concerning Acceptance of Cadets and Cadets at the Indonesian Navy Academy which does not yet contain gender equality in indicators and sub-indicators:
 - a. Technical difficulties are influenced by the prevalence of gender discrimination in cadet admissions.
 - b. Uniformity of behavior also faces obstacles experienced by cadets.
 - c. The percentage is also disproportionate where the number of cadets is still very small compared to cadets.
 - d. Clarity on the goals of gender equality has not been stated implicitly in this policy.

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- e. The lack of access from outside parties to know about admissions decision making has brought about gender equality.
 - f. Social factors still influence this because there are many views of discrimination towards cadets in society.
 - g. The group's attitudes and resources do not yet have a place to express them.
3. Implementation of Perkasal policy Number 38 of 2021 concerning Admission of Cadets and Cadets to the Indonesian Navy Academy towards gender justice in indicators and sub-indicators:
- a. The scope of the desired behavior change is quite clear.
 - b. The underlying theory is sufficient in providing gender justice.
 - c. Funding resources have been allocated properly to provide fair rights between cadets and cadets.
 - d. Implementing officials have been recruited in accordance with applicable requirements.
 - e. There is commitment and ability from implementing officials to uphold gender justice.
4. Implementation of Perkasal policy Number 38 of 2021 concerning Admission of Cadets and Cadets to the Indonesian Navy Academy which does not yet contain gender justice in indicators and sub-indicators:
- a. Technical difficulties are indicated by the ratio of cadet and cadet admissions which is still not proportional.
 - b. Uniformity of behavior: There is still a gap in action and support for cadets and cadets.
 - c. The existing gender percentage is not proportional compared to other comparisons.
 - d. Clarity of objectives is still lacking, which results in uncertainty and lack of supervision.
 - e. All levels within the Indonesian Navy Academy are involved in the decision-making process and have a good level of coordination and integration.
 - f. This decision rule is in line with the decision of the implementing body above and in accordance with applicable legal principles.
 - g. In external access, there is no open availability of information regarding the process of accepting cadets and cadets.
 - h. There are still socio-economic conditions and technological conditions that have an impact on the ease of implementing this policy.
 - i. There is a role in the level of public awareness, level of public trust and media support and public opinion which influence the implementation of this policy.
 - j. There is a level of willingness and persistence of implementing officials in implementing the policy for accepting cadets and cadets at the Indonesian Navy Academy.

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